

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Experience with a medium chain triglyceride complex and changes in mental focus and score in different modes of golf transport and play

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Abstract

Medium Chain Triglyceride (MCT)- based supplements have increased cognitive function in general and specific functional realms. Can an MCT complex improve mental focus in sports with a high, active cognitive component? This pilot investigation tested whether the proprietary MCT complex utilized could result in positive gains in mental focus or perception of enhanced energy on the course. Each of the ten subjects played a 9-hole round using a motor cart, pushcart, carry bag, or electric trolley (which simulated playing with a caddie) while wearing a portable metabolic system to determine baseline energy expenditure, mental focus, and score baseline. Data points recorded and averaged included the volume of oxygen used per minute total (VO₂/L/min), oxygen used per kg of body weight per minute (VO₂ml/kg/min), converted to kcal per hour, and heart rate. A 10-point mental focus scale had golfers rating tee shots, second through fourth shots, and the short game from 100 yards in. Using their preferred mode of transport and play, the subjects completed one more, 9-hole round after once-daily consumption of the supplement for seven days. The average rating of mental focus and perceived energy increased from a level of 5.77 to 7.22 out of 10, statistically significant at P= 0.0120. Actual play scores decreased from 10.8 to 8.9 over par for the 9-hole rounds, trending positively. This initial trial suggests that a proprietary MCT complex can improve actual golf performance and the golfer's perceptions of focus and energy regardless of which mode of transport and play is used.

Keywords: Medium chain triglycerides; Golf scores; Golf focus; Golf energy perception; Golf improvement

1. Introduction

Sports, where cognitive function and focus are essential, have not received the same supplement options for performance enhancement as those with high physical demands. Can specific supplements improve function in this arena of sports performance?

The supplement industry has exploded in the last twenty years with numerous claims for specific supplements and increased sports performance [1-4]. While bodybuilders pioneered using nutritional strategies to gain an edge, conventional exercise physiology, directly and indirectly, impacted nutrition for performance.

Exercise physiology came of age in the 1960s and 1970s, with prominent physiologists producing textbooks that clarified and defined the field and provided a springboard for additional questions about performance relationships and enhancements. Many of these early studies focused on the energy dynamics of the sport. Carbohydrate-based compounds and sports drinks were the results when paired with endurance performance [5-11].

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Increased protein consumption through supplementation received a commercial push as weight training/resistance training gained acceptance to improve sports performance [12-16]. Leading the next historical charge were compounds related to increased strength and anaerobic or sprint performance [17-21]. These compounds have evolved to include many components besides protein, aiming to improve the training experience and results.

While thinking and reaction time in sports is critical, these aspects of sports performance have received less product attention. Some supplement applications have limited investigations of cognitive benefits of sports focus and thinking [22-24]. Several of the compounds used for increasing physical performance, containing caffeine, have been applied to the mental focus arena [25, 26]. Some caffeine can improve mental focus by increasing arousal, narrowing, and heightening attention. However, this is only desirable in some sports or activities.

In sports where there is a fine motor skill component, increasing focus by increasing physiological arousal can be a detriment to performance. What the individual may gain by increased attention is offset and diminished by decreasing the ability to think broadly and the decrement in fine motor performance. In animal and human studies, a few compounds have shown promise of increasing focus and cognition without adverse motor effects from increased arousal.

In recent applications, MCT-based compounds have demonstrated increased cognition along a broad spectrum of abilities [27-30]. Moreover, it appears without any effects of incompatible arousal components, which is the potential case with compounds relying on caffeine. MCT studies have focused on the effects concerning dementia and Alzheimer's, with some investigations on non-affected individuals in this regard [31-35]. The body of work has been positive about MCT compounds improving cognitive function [36-41], with no reported adverse effects associated with caffeine. In other words, cognitive function was improved with no negative physiological or neurological ramifications.

2. Material and methods

Ten golfers were recruited: six males (n=6) and four females (n=4). All were regular participants at an accessible golf course where they were familiar with the course and terrain (Table 1). A further requirement was golf participation at least once per week at the course to ensure that both golf course familiarity and attention to mental focus were high.

Table 1 Subject Demographics

Subject	Weight	Height	Age	VO2/ml/kg/min	Max HR	AT/ml/kg/min	Handicap/9 Holes
1	220	71	69	22.8	148	19.1	12.15
2	220	74	73	29.5	138	19.4	6.9
3	163	69	69	33.9	152	22	7.26
4	165	69	48	31.8	148	21.9	0.05
5	220	74	58	30.4	144	22.4	5
6	228	71	69	25.4	124	13.9	12.1
7	105	60	59	26.9	136	19.2	6.2
8	183	65	65	20	148	13.7	16.5
9	114	67	60	26.9	131	15.5	21.5
10	183	67	66	14.5	146	12.3	21
Mean	180.10	68.7	64	26.21	141.5	17.94	10.9

Before supplementation with the proprietary MCT complex, the golfers completed trials with the selected modes of transport and play. This included a motor cart (MC), pushcart (PC), carry bag (CB), and electric trolley (ET). The subjects were measured for metabolic response during those nine-hole rounds with a VO2 Master portable analyzer [42], (Figure 1, Figure 2).

Figure 1 Subject using Pushcart with metabolic sensor

Figure 2 Golf, putting with metabolic sensor

To assess mental focus and feeling of energy in golf, the literature revealed there was no simple instrument for this purpose [43]. A short survey was developed, then tested with two golfers. Feedback resulted in minor modifications,

and the survey was converted into an online rating and assessment [44, 45]. The survey included rating tee shots, second to fourth shots, the short game defined by 100 yards, and in and feelings of energy. The survey used a ten-point rating scale. A rating of five was considered average, with scores above five indicating increased focus and energy, while those below that number indicated less-than-average values. The subjects were given additional exposure to the scale during a sister project on energy expenditure in various models of transport and play. In addition, each participant kept score.

The subjects used the energy expenditure (EE) portion to choose their preferred mode of transport and play. Nine holes were played in that mode and assessed for score and mental focus. The preferred transport/play among the subjects was six ET, one MC, two PC, and one CB. The subjects then used that same mode of play after taking the supplement for seven days, (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Supplement label

3. Results

When comparing mean energy expenditure, there was no statistically significant difference between the first round without the supplement and the second with the supplement (234.10 kcal per hour versus 232.51 kcal per hour).

Actual play scores decreased from 10.8 to 8.9 over par for the 9-hole rounds, trending positively. (Table 2, Figure 4).

Table 2 Score to par comparison, pre versus post-supplement

Subject	Mode	Score over Par 1	Score over Par 2
1	ET	10	9
2	PC	7	6
3	ET	4	4
4	CB	4	2
5	ET	5	5
6	MC	11	9
7	PC	9	2
8	ET	19	21
9	ET	21	14
10	ET	18	17
Mean		10.8	8.9

Figure 4 Score to par, graphic comparison

Rating of mental focus and energy increased from 5.72 to 7.22 out of 10, statistically significant at $P= 0.0120$. (Table 3, Figure 5).

Table 3 Mental focus comparison, pre versus post-supplement

Subject	Mode	Mental Focus 1	Mental Focus 2
1	ET	6	9.5
2	PC	5	8
3	ET	8	8
4	CB	6	8
5	ET	5	5
6	MC	5	7
7	PC	6	7.66
8	ET	5.5	5
9	ET	5.66	6
10	ET	5.5	8
Mean		5.77	7.22

Figure 5 Graphic comparison of mental focus, pre versus post

4. Discussion

This study is the first investigation to ascertain the effects of a proprietary MCT complex on mental performance in a cognitively based sport. While a limited study, this outcome indicates that MCT-based supplements can have mental focus benefits in sports like golf without increased physiological arousal. This is important as arousal levels, as indicated by heart rate and galvanic skin response, can increase to a point where they interfere with fine motor skill performance.

This brief investigation showed a difference in effect between mental focus and score to par. It is theorized that mental focus was measured on a defined, ten-point scale, in which regular golfers know their levels daily. Score to par has a wide variability as it depends upon the weather, course conditions, physical factors to the golfer in question that day, and handicap/index. Because the subjects had a wide range of handicap levels relative to par, directional trends with a simple pre and post-design are more challenging to observe and attribute without assignment to a specific sub-group and repeated measures.

With the mental focus scale results, the subjects noted that their focus and feeling of energy were enhanced. This was true even with the actual EE, as measured in O₂ and kcal per nine holes, remaining even. Previous research and applying

whole-body energy usage observations from the last 30 years aligned with this result. The exercise intensity was too low in this short golf course round for the compound's potential benefits in either total energy expenditure or measurable substrate changes.

5. Conclusion

This beta study demonstrates a potential enhancement for MCT based complexes in sports and activities where there is a high cognitive component combined with the need to not elevate physiological arousal.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the Colorado Golf Association for providing course access and usage for the study.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

NEW has no conflict of interest. GMH and RWK are scientific advisors to UBN, the manufacturer of the supplement.

Statement of ethical approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the ethics committee of the Colorado Center for Health & Sports Science, Denver, Colorado.

Statement of informed consent

Informed written consent was obtained from each participant after a clear explanation of the study objectives and procedures.

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The Colorado Golf Association provided access and play at CommonGround Golf Course for the study. Ultimate Brain Nutrients provided the supplement for the study. The Colorado Center for Health & Sports Science provided research supervision and equipment used in the study.

Author roles

NEW was primarily responsible for research design, testing, on-course measurement, and data reduction and write up. GMH assisted in research design, write up and final review. RWK contributed to write up and final review.

References

- [1] Research GV. Dietary supplements market size worth \$272.4 billion by 2028. 2021. [Available from: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/press-release/global-dietary-supplemen...> Accessed August 2021.
- [2] Kantor ED, Rehm CD, Du M, et al. Trends in dietary supplement use among US adults from 1999-2012. *Jama*. 2016, 316(14):1464–1474.
- [3] Mozaffarian D, Rosenberg I, Uauy R. History of modern nutrition science—implications for current research, dietary guidelines, and food policy *BMJ* 2018, 361:k2392
- [4] Kerksick CM, Wilborn CD, Roberts MD. et al. ISSN exercise & sports nutrition review update: research & recommendations. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr* 2018, 3-15, 38.
- [5] Widrick JJ, Costill DL, Fink WJ, Hickey MS, Mcconell GK, Tanaka H. Carbohydrate feedings and exercise performance: effect of initial muscle glycogen concentration. *J Appl Physiol*. 1993, 74(6):2998–3005.
- [6] Coyle EF, Montain SJ. Benefits of fluid replacement with carbohydrate during exercise. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*. 1992, Sep, 24(9 Suppl):S324-30.
- [7] Davis JM, Lamb DR, Pate RR, Slentz CA, Burgess WA, Bartoli WP. Carbohydrate-electrolyte drinks: effects on endurance cycling in the heat. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1988, Oct, 48(4):1023-30.

- [8] Tsintzas K, Williams C. Human muscle glycogen metabolism during exercise. Effect of carbohydrate supplementation. *Sports Med.* 1998, Jan, 25(1):7-23.
- [9] Cermak NM, Van Loon LJ. The use of carbohydrates during exercise as an ergogenic aid. *Sports Med.* 2013, 43(11):1139–55.
- [10] Noakes TD. Fluid replacement during exercise. *Exerc Sport Sci Rev.* 1993, 21:297-330.
- [11] Currell K, Jeukendrup AE. Superior endurance performance with ingestion of multiple transportable carbohydrates. *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* 2008, 40(2):275–81.
- [12] Pasiakos SM, McLellan TM, Lieberman HR. The effects of protein supplements on muscle mass, strength, and aerobic and anaerobic power in healthy adults: a systematic review. *Sports Med.* 2015, Jan, 45(1):111-31.
- [13] Tang JE, Moore DR, Kujbida GW, Tarnopolsky MA, Phillips SM. Ingestion of whey hydrolysate, casein, or soy protein isolate: effects on mixed muscle protein synthesis at rest and following resistance exercise in young men. *J Appl Physiol.* 2009, 107(3):987–92.
- [14] Morton RW, Murphy KT, Mckellar SR, Schoenfeld BJ, Henselmans M, Helms E, Aragon AA, Devries MC, Banfield L, Krieger JW, Phillips SM. A systematic review, meta-analysis and meta-regression of the effect of protein supplementation on resistance training-induced gains in muscle mass and strength in healthy adults. *Br J Sports Med.* 2018, 52(6):376–84.
- [15] Kreider RB. Dietary supplements and the promotion of muscle growth with resistance exercise. *Sports Med.* 1999, 27(2):97–110.
- [16] Tarnopolsky MA. Protein and physical performance. *Curr Opin Clin Nutr Metab Care.* 1999, 2(6):533–7.
- [17] Lemon PW, Tarnopolsky MA, Macdougall JD, Atkinson SA. Protein requirements and muscle mass/strength changes during intensive training in novice bodybuilders. *J Appl Physiol.* 1992, 73(2):767–75.
- [18] Clarkson PM, Rawson ES. Nutritional supplements to increase muscle mass. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 1999, 39(4):317–28.
- [19] Campbell B, Wilborn C, La Bounty P, Taylor L, Nelson MT, Greenwood M, Ziegenfuss TN, Lopez HL, Hoffman JR, Stout JR, Schmitz S, Collins R, Kalman DS, Antonio J, Kreider RB. International society of sports nutrition position stand: energy drinks. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2013, 10(1):1.
- [20] Harty PS, Zabriskie HA, Erickson JL, Molling PE, Kerksick CM, Jagim AR. Multi-ingredient pre-workout supplements, safety implications, and performance outcomes: a brief review. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2018, Aug 8, 15(1):41.
- [21] Stratton MT, Siedler MR, Harty PS, Rodriguez C, Boykin JR, Green JJ, Keith DS, White SJ, DeHaven B, Williams AD, Tinsley GM. The influence of caffeinated and non-caffeinated multi-ingredient pre-workout supplements on resistance exercise performance and subjective outcomes. *J Int Soc Sports Nutr.* 2022, Apr 4, 19(1):126-149.
- [22] Mcnaughton LR, Lovell RJ, Siegler J, Midgley AW, Moore L, Bentley DJ. The effects of caffeine ingestion on time trial cycling performance. *Int J Sports Physiol Perform.* 2008, 3(2):157–63.
- [23] Cappelletti S, Daria P, Sani G, et al. Caffeine: cognitive and physical performance enhancer or psychoactive drug? *Curr Neuropharmacol.* 2015, 13(1):71–88.
- [24] Childs E. Influence of energy drink ingredients on mood and cognitive performance. *Nutr Rev.* 2014, 72(suppl_1):48–59.
- [25] Giles GE, Mahoney CR, Brunyé TT, et al. Differential cognitive effects of energy drink ingredients: caffeine, taurine, and glucose. *Pharmacol Biochem Behav.* 2012, 102(4):569–577.
- [26] Alford C, Cox H, Wescott R. The effects of red bull energy drink on human performance and mood. *Amino Acids.* 2001, 21(2):139-50.
- [27] Babayan VK. Medium chain length fatty acid esters and their medical and nutritional applications. *J Am Oil Chem Soc* 1981, 58, 49A–51A.
- [28] Greenberger NJ, Skillman TG. Medium-chain triglycerides. *N Engl J Med.* 1969, May 8, 280(19):1045-58.
- [29] Croteau, E., Castellano, C. A., Richard, M. A., Fortier, M., Nugent, S., Lepage, M., Duchesne, S., Whittingstall, K., Turcotte, É. E., Bocti, C., Fülöp, T., & Cunnane, S. C. (2018). Ketogenic Medium Chain Triglycerides Increase Brain Energy Metabolism in Alzheimer's Disease. *Journal of Alzheimer's disease.* 2018, JAD, 64(2), 551–561.

- [30] Daou M, Montagner Sassi J, Miller MW, et al. Effects of a multi-ingredient energy supplement on cognitive performance and cerebral-cortical activation. *J Diet Suppl.* 2019, 16(2):129–140.
- [31] Giannos P., Prokopidis K., Lidoriki I., Triantafyllidis KK, Kechagias KS., Celoch K, Candow DG, Ostojic SM, & Forbes S C. Medium-chain triglycerides may improve memory in non-demented older adults: a systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *BMC geriatrics.* 2022., 22(1), 817.
- [32] Ota M, Matsuo J, Ishida I, Takano H, Yokoi Y, Hori H, Yoshida S, Ashida K, Nakamura K, Takahashi T, Kunugi H. Effects of a medium-chain triglyceride-based ketogenic formula on cognitive function in patients with mild-to-moderate Alzheimer's disease. *Neurosci Lett.* 2019, Jan 18, 690:232-236.
- [33] Lilamand M, Porte B, Cognat E, Hugon J, Mouton-Liger F, Paquet C. Are ketogenic diets promising for Alzheimer's disease? A translational review. *Alzheimers Res Ther.* 2020, Apr 14, 12(1):42.
- [34] Ross SM. Coconut Oil: Effects of Medium-Chain Triglycerides for Prevention and Treatment of Alzheimer Disease. *Holist Nurs Pract.* 2021, Jan-Feb 01, 35(1):49-50.
- [35] Mutoh T, Kunitoki K, Tatewaki Y, Yamamoto S, Thyreau B, Matsudaira I, Kawashima R, Taki Y. Impact of medium-chain triglycerides on gait performance and brain metabolic network in healthy older adults: a double-blind, randomized controlled study. *Geroscience.* 2022, 44(3):1325-1338.
- [36] Wolkodoff NE, Haase GM. A Phytonutrient Based Brain Activation Complex and Short-Term Brain Function Changes: An Initial Investigation. *Ann Rev Resear.* 2021, 6(5): 555697.
- [37] Kovács Z, Brunner B, Ari C. Beneficial Effects of Exogenous Ketogenic Supplements on Aging Processes and Age-Related Neurodegenerative Diseases. *Nutrients.* 2021, Jun 26, 13(7):2197.
- [38] Maalouf M, Rho JM, Mattson MP. The neuroprotective properties of calorie restriction, the ketogenic diet, and ketone bodies. *Brain Res Rev.* 2009, Mar, 59(2):293-315.
- [39] Krikorian R, Shidler MD, Dangelo K, Couch SC, Benoit SC, Clegg DJ. Dietary ketosis enhances memory in mild cognitive impairment. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2012, Feb, 33(2):425.e19-27.
- [40] Juby AG, Blackburn TE, Mager DR. Use of medium chain triglyceride (MCT) oil in subjects with Alzheimer's disease: A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, crossover study, with an open-label extension. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y).* 2022, Mar 14, 8(1):e12259.
- [41] Pan Y. Nutrients, Cognitive Function, and Brain Aging: What We Have Learned from Dogs. *Med Sci (Basel).* 2021, Nov 18, 9(4):72.
- [42] Montoye AHK, Vondrasek JD, Hancock JB. Validity and Reliability of the VO2 Master Pro for Oxygen Consumption and Ventilation Assessment. *International Journal of Exercise Science.* 2020, Vol.13:(4):1382 - 1401.
- [43] Selicki FA, Segall E. The mind/body connection of the golf swing. *Clin Sports Med.* 1996, Jan, 15(1):191-201.
- [44] Kendzierski D, DeCarlo KJ. Physical activity enjoyment scale: Two validation studies. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology.* 1991, 13:50–64.
- [45] Yost M, Strauss R, Davis R. The effectiveness of the "golfer's groove" in improving golfers' scores. *Res Q.* 1976, Oct, 47(3):569-73.